

Hydrothermal alteration and its effects on Ti-V deportment and processing of the Middle Ore Layer (MOL) from the Mustavaara Fe-Ti-V deposit, Finland

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Introduction

The Mustavaara Fe-Ti-V deposit located 53 km southwest of Kuusamo, northern Finland, represents a significant vanadium resource hosted within the Koillismaa (2.44 Ga) layered intrusion complex. As part of the Horizon Europe AVANTI^S (HE AVANTI^S)-project, this study investigates the impact of hydrothermal alteration on titanium and vanadium deportment within the Middle Ore Layer (MOL) of the Mustavaara deposit. The research contributes to AVANTI^S's goal of developing innovative solutions for sustainable vanadium and titanium production in Europe by providing a detailed understanding of the distribution of critical and strategic elements within the Mustavaara and other oxide deposits in Europe.

Preliminary results

The mineralogical investigation of two drill cores (MV-63-2011 and MV-64-2011) reveals distinct alteration patterns. MV-63 shows extensive hydrothermal alteration with elevated content of V and Ti hosted in silicate minerals. In contrast, MV-64 exhibits better-preserved ilmenomagnetite grains and titanite at magnetite-ilmenite contacts. The presence of secondary calcite, epidote and other calcium-bearing minerals suggest the involvement of carbonate rich hydrothermal fluids. Based on mass balance calculations, magnetite and ilmenite remain the primary hosts for Ti and V, although a significant amount of V (30%) locates in silicate minerals, particularly in secondary amphiboles and epidotes (Figure 1).

The findings highlight that a considerable amount of Ti and V are mobilized and reprecipitated in secondary silicate phases. This hydrothermal mineralization may complicate ore processing and pose recovery challenges that could necessitate adjustment of processing strategies. While primary recovery should focus on oxide-hosted portions, the significant titanite amount represents a potential secondary source of titanium. Vanadium recovery strategies must account for substantial silicate hosting which can be a resource for the future. Future work within the AVANTI^S framework will focus on optimizing processing strategies and enhancing the cost-efficient and sustainable extraction of these critical raw materials.

Figure 1. EPMA elemental mapping revealing vanadium-enriched epidote from drill core MV-63-2011, sample -253. The presence of V in silicate phases, particularly epidote, indicates significant hydrothermal alteration and remobilization of vanadium from primary oxide minerals. This observation has important implications for processing strategies, as substantial portions of vanadium is located in silicate minerals rather than being confined to oxide phases.

Acknowledgments

This research is a part of the doctoral study project of M. Markkanen, which is funded by the HE AVANTI^S project. HE AVANTI^S is funded by the European Union. The doctoral study project and HE AVANTI^S project are implemented in close collaboration with the Geological Survey of Finland.